

Title: Fundamentals of Robotics Technology

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INTRODUCTION:

Resuming the main aspects I already explained you are enough for sending the contract as advisor by Email. There were some grammar mistakes because my first language is not English and I am busy here. If you send the contract as Advisor by E-mail I will be able to Explain you how to build very advanced things. In any case that is what you will need to do as first important step. There are people who want to be in charge of space programs after selling cars or a few things to NASA or because they are billionaires and want more billionaires. Those are not the right procedures. For Example. Those people are good for organizing things but not for Expert Analyst on Systems and Technologies. Wrong procedures can make you lose thousands of years on technological aspects or even millions of years. Best Regards !!

_This messenger does not have edit button. It is like the Youtube, it took them 5 years for the edit button and after making many complains. Resuming: the main aspects I already explained you are enough for sending the contract as advisor by Email. There were some grammar mistakes because my first language is not English and I am busy here. If you send the contract as Advisor by E-mail I will be able to Explain you how to build very advanced things. In any case that is what you will need to do as first important step. There are people who want to be in charge of Space Programs after selling cars or a few things to NASA or because they are billionaires and they want to be more billionaires. Those are not the right procedures. For Example. Those people are good for organizing things but not for Expert Analyst on Systems and Technologies. Wrong procedures can make you lose thousands of years on technological aspects or even millions of years.